

DIMITRIE CANTEMIR
UNIVERSITY
Tirgu Mures

11TH EDITION

THE INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

GLOBALIZATION, INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE AND NATIONAL IDENTITY

18-19 MAY 2024

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CONFERENCE SCHEDULE

SATURDAY – 18 MAY 2024

ON-LINE EDITION

10⁰⁰ - 11⁰⁰ - Welcome and Opening

11⁰⁰ - 13⁰⁰ – Paper Presentations on Sections:

- **Literature**
- **Language and Discourse**
- **Communication, Journalism, Education Sciences, Psychology and Sociology**
- **History, Political Sciences, International Relations**
- **Social Sciences**

14⁰⁰ - 18⁰⁰ - Paper Presentations on Sections

**The conference is organised in partnership by:
"Alpha" Institute for Multicultural Studies
"Gh. Șincai" Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities
"Dimitrie Cantemir" University of Tîrgu-Mureș**

A WORD
FROM THE PRESIDENT OF THE CONFERENCE

DEAR GUESTS,

Having established a certain tradition in the recent years, the International Conference *GLOBALIZATION, INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE AND NATIONAL IDENTITY* (now at its 11th edition) intends to unite emerging scholars, as well as prestigious researchers from different fields of radical relevance for the contemporary society, a society that is supposed to secure its future not only on the economic and ecological level, but also on the spiritual one. Literature, the cultural discourses as well as the arts gain new connections and dimensions through fundamental changes and structural progress, so that the social end-results of education and research becomes extremely important. It is a fact that in our postmodern times, we live in a society of knowledge, from which we benefit directly in our everyday life, but to the risks and dangers of which we are at the same time exposed. *Non scholae sed vitae discimus* (*We do not learn for the school, but for life*) becomes a creed that every academic institution has to put into practice by means of its activities. It is essential that the path between education and research is very short, especially in academic systems. Research generates new knowledge, creates a favourable atmosphere for change, and provides people with information and data which help them to become aware of the mysteries of the universe and to make the most of their activity in all fields of knowledge. In this interesting and captivating century, to the noble mission of educating the younger generations we must also add the fruit of the efforts in research, materialized in interesting works and papers, together with ideas generated by the creative ability which ennobles the personality of the academic.

I wish to express my hope that this scientific event will take place under the most favourable auspices and that it will represent a remarkable starting point for further evolution and development in the field of knowledge. Let this international conference provide a good opportunity for us to gain and transfer knowledge, to generate new theories in the world of science – essential aspirations of any contemporary research.

Prof. IULIAN BOLDEA, PhD
President of the *GIDNI 11* Conference

SATURDAY – 18 MAY 2024

LITERATURE

Moderators: Prof. Iulian Boldea, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Assoc. Prof. Emanuela Ilie, PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași; Assoc. Prof. Dumitru-Mircea Buda, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș.

1. Iulian Boldea, Prof. PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *NICOLAE MANOLESCU BETWEEN CRITICISM AND LITERARY HISTORY*
2. Ștefan Lucian Mureșanu, Prof., PhD, „Hyperion” University of Bucharest, *NICHITA STĂNESCU'S ELEGIES AND THEIR AFFECTIVE NONNERVES*
3. Emanuela Ilie, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THANATOGRAPHY AND EXILAR CONDITION IN GABRIELA MELINESCU'S POETRY*
4. Luiza Catrinel Marinescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University St Kliment Ohridsky, Sofia, *A FORM OF CULTURAL DIPLOMACY, THE ROMANIAN GRAMMAR FOR FOREIGNERS: VASILE ALECSANDRI, A CASE STUDY*
5. Clementina Alexandra Mihăilescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Aurel Vlaicu” University of Arad, Stela Pleșa, PhD, Gymnasium School, Racovița, Sibiu County, *ILLUSION VS REALITY IN FITZGERALD'S NOVEL THE GREAT GATSBY*
6. Mariana Baloșescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *BIBLICAL THINKING AND MODERN THINKING: THE BOOK OF JONAH FROM THE OLD TESTAMENT AND MARIN SORESCU'S IONA*

7. Nicoleta Călina, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *DORA D'ISTRIA: ANELLO DI CIVILTÀ FRA L'ORIENTE E L'OCCIDENTE*
8. Marius-Valeriu Grecu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *THE UNIVERSE OF THE MYTH AND THE FANTASTIC – ENDLESS SOURCES OF INSPIRATION IN ROMANIAN LITERATURE*
9. Dana-Eugenia Dughi, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Aurel Vlaicu” University of Arad, Patricia – Jana – Maria Bota (Ruzsicska), Foreign Language Instructor, PhD, „Fokus” Educational Center of Foreign Languages, Arad, *ENCHANTMENT AS A TEXT, THE STRUCTURE AND POETICS OF THE ENCHANTMENT*
10. Irina-Ana Drobot, Lecturer, PhD, Technical University of Civil Engineering, Bucharest, *REFERENCES TO NICHITA STĂNESCU'S POETIC UNIVERSE IN HAIKU: THE CASE OF AN ONLINE HAIKU WRITERS' COMMUNITY*
11. Irina-Ana Drobot, Lecturer, PhD, Technical University of Civil Engineering, Bucharest, *PROJECTING PERSONAL EMOTIONS ON THE NATURAL SETTING DURING AUTUMN*
12. Anuța Ionescu, Senior Lecturer, PhD, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica, Bucharest, *THE LAST NIGHT OF LOVE, THE FIRST NIGHT OF WAR- A SUBJECTIVE NOVEL*
13. Ileana Botescu Sirețeanu, Lecturer, PhD, „Transilvania” University of Brașov, *LITERATURE AND GLOBALIZATION: RETHINKING DIFFERENCE, NARRATIVE AND TRANSCULTURALITY*

14. Iudit Călinescu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Szeged, *MYTHICAL SOURCES IN THE POEM „PARADIS ÎN DESTRĂMARE”, BY LUCIAN BLAGA*
15. Maria Lațchici, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *HISTORICAL THEMES IN IVAN ARALICA'S PROSE*
16. Iulian Băicuș, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *THE JOURNAL OF ANDRÉ GIDE*
17. Oana-Andreea Ghiță-Pîrnuță, Senior Lecturer, PhD, „Transilvania” University of Brașov, *ACQUIRING STRENGTH FROM LIFE: THE PUZZLE OF ANTONIO'S QUEST FOR IDENTITY IN ANAYA'S FICTION*
18. Adriana Elena Geantă, Lecturer, PhD, University of Pitești, Irina Bărbieru, Educator for preschool education, Pitești, *THE IMPORTANCE OF STIMULATE STUDENTS' INTEREST IN READING*
19. Nicoleta Sălcudeanu, Scientific Researcher, PhD, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities of the Romanian Academy, Târgu Mureș, *TO BUILD AMONG THE RUINS*
20. Mariana Cocieru, Scientific researcher, PhD, Institute of Romanian Philology „Bogdan Petriceicu-Hasdeu”, Moldova State University, *FUNERAL RITUAL CREATIONS – FORMS OF EXPRESSING SUFFERING AND FINDING SOLACE IN THE "GREAT PASSAGE" TO THE WORLD "BEYOND"*
21. Diana Stroescu, Research Assistant, PhD, „A. Philippide” Institute of Romanian Philology, Romanian Academy, Iași, *MEMORY AND IDENTITY DURING THE GREAT MILITARY CONFLICTS*
22. Roxana Silvia Moraru, Assist. Prof., PhD, “Vasile Goldiș” Western University of Arad, *VENICE, A NEXUS OF BEAUTY, ARTISTS, MUSIC, LOVE AND FULFILLED DESTINY*

23. Monica Alina Toma, Assist. Prof., PhD, Academy of Economic Studies, Bucharest, *METAMORPHOSES OF THE WOMAN IN PABLO NERUDA'S LOVE POETRY*
24. Ioana-Mihaela Vultur, PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *ANA BLANDIANA, A MODEL OF ETHICAL ILINX*
25. Iuliana Miu, PhD, University of Bucharest, *MIRCEA NEDELICIU AND CINEMATOGRAPHY*
26. Dimitrie Andrei Borcan, PhD, *FROM HORROR NOVELS TO HORROR FILMS - STEPHEN KING'S THE SHINING AND CHRISTINE: CRIMINAL CHARACTERS, ARCHETYPAL SYMBOLS AND MOTIFS*
27. Camelia Ioana Ienciu (Popa), PhD, *HAYDEN WHITE AND THE VALUE OF NARRATIVITY IN THE REPRESENTATION OF REALITY*
28. Amalia-Maria Roșioru, PhD, „Ovidius” University of Constanța, *THE INFLUENCE OF THE NEW NOVEL IN SORIN TITEL'S PROSE*
29. Cristina Chifane, PhD, Independent Scholar, *IN-BETWEENNESS OR A MATTER OF IDENTITY IN JHUMPA LAHIRI'S IN OTHER WORDS (2016) AND WHEREABOUTS (2021)*
30. Cosmina Andreea Roșu, PhD, University of Pitești, *THE MYTH OF PERSONALITY AND THE CONSCIOUSNESS OF DEATH*
31. Ramona Buruiană, PhD, „Virgil Madgearu” Economic College, Galați, *IN MEMORIAM MILAN KÚNDERA - WEIGHT OR „THE UNBEARABLE LIGHTNESS OF BEING”*
32. Anca Rusu, PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *PAUL ZARIFOPOL CASE. THE EUROPEAN MUTILATED BY COMPLACENT LITERARY BALKANISM*
33. Elena-Silvia Terpan, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, University

- Center Pitești, *THE REPRESENTATION OF NATIONAL CONSCIOUSNESS, FROM EMINESCU AND VIERU'S PERSPECTIVE*
34. Ozana-Ioana Ciobanu, PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *MAGIC REALISM IN THE ROMANIAN PRESS*
35. Maria Bîscal (Oprea), PhD Student, „1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *THE SEARCH FOR BEING BETWEEN REPETITION AND LIMINALITY*
36. Adriana Maria Călugăr (Cutean), PhD Student, „1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *THE ROLE OF FAITH AND PRAYER IN THE RESISTANCE OF INMATES FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF MEMORIAL LITERATURE*
37. Andra-Ioana Pușcoci, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *CONFRONTING THE PAST IN MILAN KUNDERA'S NOVEL IGNORANCE*
38. Andra-Astrid Belibou, PhD Student, „Ovidius” University of Constanța, *RACIAL AND ETHNIC METAPHORS IN YOUNG ADULT FAIRY TALE RETELLINGS*
39. Mihaela-Niculina Jurje (Tănasă), PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, North University Centre of Baia Mare, *LOVE – THE ROAD TO SELF-FULFILLMENT. "O FEMEIE PENTRU APOCALIPS (A WOMAN FOR THE APOCALYPSE)", VINTILĂ HORIA. CHARACTERS*
40. Porfirie Pescaru, PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *VISIONS ON INTERIORITY: MARCUS AURELIUS AND SAINT AUGUSTINE*
41. Silvia-Ofelia Chelariu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, *MIHAI EMINESCU. THE JOURNEY - BETWEEN MYTH AND METAPHOR*

42. Georgiana-Adriana Tituleac, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE ROMANTIC IMAGINARY IN EMIL BOTTA'S POETRY*
43. Alexandra Ruscanu, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *REPRESENTATIONS OF FEMININITY IN THE CULTURAL SPACE*
44. Alina-Georgiana Butoi (Petre), PhD Student, „Ovidius” University of Constanța, *CONSUMER IDENTITY. CONSUMERISM AND PSYCHOSOMATIC RESPONSES IN B.E.ELLIS' AMERICAN PSYCHO*
45. Ana-Maria Plumb, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE IMAGE OF THE COMMUNIST WOMAN IN ROMANIAN LITERATURE*
46. Bianca Roman, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *THE ART OF MUSIC - A LITERARY TOOL FOR MANAGING NARRATIVE EMPATHY IN "SERENADĂ PENTRU NADIA (SERENADE FOR NADIA)" NOVEL BY ZÜLFÜ LIVANELI*
47. Camelia-Vasilica Munteanu (Gheorghisor), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica, Bucharest, *REMEMBER - A UNIQUE AESTHETIC OF MYSTERY*
48. Marinela-Alexandra Enache-Popa, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *E.M. CIORAN ET LA RÉTROSPECTIVE D'UNE INTRANSIGEANCE ARDENTE POUR DÉCODER LE PESSIMISME*
49. Ioana Pordea, PhD Student, University of Oradea, *LITERARY MOTIFS IN THE LAMENTS FROM BEIUȘULUI COUNTY*
50. Elena-Luiza Ilie (Negură), PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *SANDA STOLOJAN - BEYOND THE CURTAIN OF THE PARISIAN EXILE*
51. Maria-Adina Gherghin (Necșoiu), PhD Student, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *EXPLORATIONS OF RUPTURE: FROM FRENCH LITERATURE TO THE PLURALITY OF*

ACADEMIC FIELDS (THE IMPLICATIONS OF RUPTURE IN FRENCH LITERATURE THROUGH THE NOVELS L'ÉTERNEL FIANCÉ BY AGNÈS DESARTHE AND LA FILLE QU'ON APPELLE BY TANGUY VIEL, AS WELL AS ITS ANALYSIS IN OTHER ACADEMIC DISCIPLINES)

52. Maximiliana Ștefan (Miheț), PhD Student, „1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *ASPECTS OF BENGESKIAN CITIZENSHIP*
53. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE CRITICISM OF TOTALITARIAN SOCIETY - EUGÈNE IONESCO AND DANIIL KHARMS. THE WORK CASES OF THE KILLER AND ELISAVETA BAM*
54. Carmen Gabriela Popa, PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *ABOUT THE EFFECT OF LITERATURE ON THE READER*
55. Rebeca-Daniela Stănescu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, Pitești University Center, *URMUZ AND THE TWISTED FAIRY TALE*
56. Smărăndița-Elena Costin, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE REVIVAL OF PENELOPE. THE IMAGINARY OF FEMINITY IN IOANA CRĂCIUNESCU'S POETRY*
57. Roxana-Gina Tituleac, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *PRE-ROMANTIC AND ROMANTIC INFLUENCES IN MATEIU CARAGIALE'S POETRY*
58. Ana-Maria Torkos, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE FEMME FATALE IN 'THE LADY OF THE HOUSE OF LOVE' BY ANGELA CARTER*
59. Valentina Gherghină, PhD Student, „1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *BEYOND BORDERS: GLOBALIZATION AND IDENTITY IN PATTERN RECOGNITION BY WILLIAM GIBSON*

60. Elena-Daniela Gorovei, PhD Student, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *THE FAILURE OF HEALING OR THE IMAGE OF A PUER AETERNUS IN THE NOVEL THE SUMMER MY MOTHER HAD GREEN EYES BY TATIANA ȚÎBULEAC*
61. Diana Ioana Faur (Feurdean), PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *SEMANTIC FIELDS OF SILENCE OF THE WORLD /SILENCE OF THE HUMAN BEING IN LUCIAN BLAGA’S LYRIC*
62. Ionela Florina Bolbea (Ene), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, Pitești University Center, *REFLECTIONS UPON POETIC TRANSLATIONS. A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE INTERPRETATIONS OF CORNELIU POPESCU AND DIMITRIE CUCLIN IN THE POEM LACUL BY MIHAI EMINESCU*
63. Aurelia-Gabriela Ardușătan (Vanca), PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, North University Centre of Baia Mare, *THE POETICS OF OCTAVIAN PALER (THE 50S AND 60S)*
64. Anamaria Mihăilă (Dumitru), PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *EAST-EUROPEAN TRACES IN DEFINING POSSIBLE WORLDS. TOMA PAVEL AND LUBOMÍR DOLEŽEL*
65. Manuela Pinteau, PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, *PATRICK SÜSKIND, ESSAY WRITER*
66. Mihaela Necula, PhD Student, „G. Călinescu” Institute of History and Literary Theory, Romanian Academy, *CEREMONIAL SCENES IN LITERATURE: „CONDICA CE ARE ÎNTRU SÎNE OBICEIURI VECHI ȘI NOUĂ A PREAÎNĂLȚĂȚILOR DOMNI”, BY CHANCELLOR GHEORGACHI (1762)*
67. Mihaela Necula, PhD Student, „G. Călinescu” Institute of History and Literary Theory, Romanian Academy, *THE BEGINNINGS OF CEREMONIAL IN OLD ROMANIAN*

*LITERATURE: „OBICEIURI VECHI ȘI NOI DE LA CURȚILE
DOMNEȘTI ROMÂNEȘTI”*

68. Elvira Buzoianu-Ambrinoc, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, Pitești University Center, *DISCOURSE TRADITIONS IN CREANGĂ'S FAIRY TALES. NARRATIVE PLAN VS. DIALOGUED PLAN*

SATURDAY – 18 MAY 2024

LANGUAGE AND DISCOURSE

Moderators: Prof. Floriana Popescu, PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați; Assoc. Prof. Ioana-Crina Prodan, PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava; Assoc. Prof. Viorica Lifari, PhD, Free International University of Moldova

1. Floriana Popescu, Prof., PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *ETHONYMS IN ENGLISH AND ROMANIAN IDIOMS*
2. Ștefan Lucian Mureșanu, Prof., PhD, „Hyperion” University of Bucharest, *NICHITA STĂNESCU'S ELEGIES AND THEIR AFFECTIVE NONNERVES*
3. Diana Dănișor, Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, Georgeta Amelia Motoi, Lecturer, PhD, University of Craiova, *THE IMPACT OF PSYCHOLINGUISTICS ON THE INTERPRETATION OF PERFORMATIVE VERBS IN THE LEGAL DISCOURSE*
4. Ioana-Crina Prodan, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *DE LA PLURISCIPLINARITÉ DANS L'ANALYSE DES DISCOURS*
5. Imola Katalin Nagy, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Sapientia” University of Cluj-Napoca, *A PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF A DOCUMENT: THE GUIDELINES FOR INCLUSIVE COMMUNICATION*
6. Oana-Maria Păstae, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Constantin Brâncuși” University of Târgu-Jiu, *THE IMPACT OF INTEGRATING NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION IN EFL CLASS*
7. Viorica Lifari, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Free International University of Moldova, *THE CONCEPT OF REGRET EXPRESSED IN THE SHORT STORY “REGRET” BY KATE CHOPIN*

8. Reka Suba, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Sapientia” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE FUNCTION OF TITLES IN JOURNALISTIC TEXTS*
9. Reka Suba, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Sapientia” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE STRUCTURE OF TITLES IN THE CASE OF INFORMATIVE TEXTS*
10. Lavinia Suciu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Politehnica University of Timișoara, Mircea Berzovan, „Nikolaus Lenau” High School Timișoara, Computer scientist, *(RE)CONSTRUCTING THE MEANING OF MULTIMODAL DISCOURSE. FOCUS ON THE VISUAL ACCESSIBILITY*
11. Elena-Laura Vulpoi, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Vasile Goldiș” Western University of Arad, *SUBTITLING BETWEEN TRANSLATION AND INTERPRETATION*
12. Ștefan Dumitru, Lecturer, PhD, “Carol I” National Defence University, Bucharest, *THE TRANSLATION OF GREEK IDIOMS (DIFFICULTIES AND SOLUTIONS)*
13. Alina-Paula Neamțu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, *DIGITAL COMMUNICATION ON THE EVE OF ELECTIONS - ISSUES OF POLITICAL NAME-CALLING ON SOCIAL MEDIA*
14. Angelica Preda, Lecturer, PhD, University of Craiova, *SPECIALISED LEXICON*
15. Cristina-Dana Popescu, Lecturer, PhD, „Ovidius” University of Constanța, *ENHANCING LEARNING PROCESSES THROUGH NEUROLINGUISTICS: ACTIVE LISTENING AND METAMODEL APPLICATION IN EXPLORING THE TIMELINE TECHNIQUE*
16. Dana Carmen Zechia, Lecturer, PhD, „Mircea cel Bătrân” Naval Academy of Constanța, *WRITING SKILL AS A COMMUNICATIVE PROCESS*
17. Oana-Maria Franțescu, Lecturer, PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *AMBIGUITY IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ROMANIAN*
18. Ileana Silvia Ciornei, Lecturer, PhD, Politehnica National University of Science and Technology, Bucharest, Pitești

University Centre, *NATIVE AMERICAN LOAN WORDS INTO ENGLISH*

19. Aurora-Tatiana Dina, Assist. Prof., PhD, Politehnica National University of Science and Technology, Bucharest, *EDUCATIONAL PODCASTS AS A MEANS OF ENHANCING STUDENT PARTICIPATION IN LEARNING ROMANIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE – CASE STUDY: THE PREPARATORY YEAR STUDENTS AT POLITEHNICA BUCHAREST, PITESTI UNIVERSITY CENTER*
20. Liliana Tronea-Ghidel, Assist. Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *EXPLORING MISLEADING MEANINGS IN ENGLISH-SPANISH FALSE FRIENDS*
21. Liliana Tronea-Ghidel, Assist. Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *AN EXPLORATION OF LOVE-RELATED IDIOMS IN ENGLISH*
22. Dana-Luminița Teleoacă (Dobre), Scientific Researcher II, PhD, „Iorgu Iordan – Alexandru Rosetti”, Institute of Linguistics of the Romanian Academy, Bucharest, *THE LATIN PAGANUS IN ROMANIAN AND OTHER ROMANCE LANGUAGES*
23. Valeria Maftai, PhD, „Ion Luca Caragiale” National College, Ploiești, *PARTICULARITIES OF THE DIALOGUE IN REALITY SHOWS*
24. Albina Puskás-Bajkó, PhD, „Bolyai Farkas” High School, Târgu Mureș, *EQUIVALENCE IN TRANSLATION, A CATCH 22*
25. Emilia-Mihaela Costescu (Crînguș), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *POLYSEMY IN THE CURRENT JOURNALISTIC LANGUAGE*
26. Réka Incze (Kutasi), PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *SOCIAL MEDIA - A PROMOTER OF EATING DISORDERS*
27. Emilia-Mihaela Costescu (Crînguș), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *PARONYMY IN THE CURRENT JOURNALISTIC LANGUAGE*

28. Alexandra Moldovan, PhD Student, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *CHALLENGES OF VISUALLY IMPAIRED NOVICE ROMANIAN TRANSLATORS*
29. Andreea Dietrich, PhD Student, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *BRIDGING WORLD: EXPLORING INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE IN CHINESE AND ENGLISH*
30. Robert Claudiu Bălăiasa, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *PERSUASIVE STRATEGIES IN THE TELEVISED POLITICAL DISCOURSE DURING THE PANDEMIC*
31. Cristina-Ileana Căndea-Axinte (Bălos), PhD Student, „Transilvania” University of Brașov, *THE ARGUMENTATIVE NATURE OF TEXT REVIEWS*
32. Boróka-Emese Salamon, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE MORPHEMIC STRUCTURE OF TOPONYMS IN ROMANIAN AND HUNGARIAN LANGUAGE. A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS*
33. Lavinia Bob, PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, North University Centre of Baia Mare, *THE MACRO-COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE FRENCH AND ROMANIAN LEGAL SYSTEMS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE LEGAL TRANSLATOR*
34. Iuliana Nedelcu (Neacșu), PhD Student, „Ovidius” University of Constanța, *THE PRESENCE OF ANGLICISM IN THE CURRENT ROMANIAN LANGUAGE*
35. Oana Balan, PhD Student, State University of Moldova, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *COGNITIVE STEREOTYPING IN ENGLISH, FRENCH AND ROMANIAN ANTONYMIC PHRASEOLOGIES FOR ‘SUCCESS’ AND ‘UNSUCCESS’*
36. Oana Șulic, PhD Student, State University of Moldova, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *EMBODIED DREAMS AS ASPIRATION: EXPLORING SOCIO-CULTURAL VARIATIONS IN METAPHORICAL EXPRESSIONS ACROSS ENGLISH, FRENCH AND ROMANIAN*

37. Ana-Maria Grigore, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *ONOMASIOLOGICAL AND SEMASIOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN THE WRITINGS OF GABRIEL GARCÍA MÁRQUEZ*
38. Mirela-Simona Gurau (Rusu), PhD Student, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF THE ROMANIAN MEDICAL LANGUAGE*
39. Andrei-Ionuț Popa, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *FOLK ETYMOLOGY AND RELATED PHENOMENA*
40. Andrei-Ionuț Popa, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *FOLK ETYMOLOGY, SUPREME ROLE IN ETHNOBOTANICAL NOMENCLATURE*
41. Mihaela Voicu-Stanciu, PhD Student, Politehnica National University of Science and Technology, Bucharest, Pitești University Centre, *DISCOURSE TRADITIONS IN LIVIU REBREANU’S NOVELS JAR AND AMÂNDOI*

SATURDAY – 18 MAY 2024

***COMMUNICATION, JOURNALISM, EDUCATION
SCIENCES, PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIOLOGY***

Moderators: Prof. Maria-Ana Georgescu, PhD, UMGST G.E. Palade of Târgu-Mureş; Assoc. Prof. Laura Ioana Leon, PhD, Grigore T. Popa University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iaşi; Assoc. Prof. Aliona Afanas, PhD, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University, Chişinău

1. Teodor Pătrăuță, Prof., PhD, „Vasile Goldiș” West University of Arad, *POSSIBILITIES AND LIMITS IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION*
2. Nicolae George Drăgulănescu, Prof., PhD, Politehnica University of Bucharest, Remus Chină, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "Dimitrie Cantemir" Christian University, Bucharest, *THE TEACHER'S COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN THE EDTECH ERA - AN ESSENTIAL ENABLER OF QUALITY ASSURANCE OF EDUCATION*
3. Mihaela Stoica, Prof., PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureş, *SELF-DISCOVERY, THE FORMATION OF SELF-IMAGE*
4. Mihaela Stoica, Prof., PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureş, *THE ROLE OF THE MANAGER IN SHAPING ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE*
5. Maria-Ana Georgescu, Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureş, *WOMEN'S PROFILE IN THE COMMUNITY*
6. Aliona Afanas, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University, Chişinău, Republic of Moldova, *THE METACOGNITION – AN INTEGRAL ELEMENT IN THE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS*

7. Victoria Maximciuc, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Institute for Research, Innovation and Technological Transfer, "Ion Creangă" State Pedagogical University, Chişinău, Republic of Moldova, *THE IMPACT OF MOTIVATION ON THE WELL-BEING OF STUDENTS WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES*
8. Angelica Hobjilă, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iaşi, *MANAGING EMOTIONS - BENCHMARKS FROM THE ROMANIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE TEXTBOOKS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL*
9. Laura Ioana Leon, Assoc. Prof., PhD, “Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iaşi, *APPROACHING MEDICINE THROUGH AN INTERDISCIPLINARY LENS: INITIATORY STEPS IN THE ROMANIAN CONTEXT*
10. Lia Lucia Epure, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Vasile Goldiș” Western University of Arad, Adrian Păcurar, Lecturer, PhD, „Vasile Goldiș” Western University of Arad, *PUBLIC COMMUNICATION IN EXTREME CRISES. PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS, TECHNIQUES AND FAILURE*
11. Angela Potâng, Assoc. Prof., PhD, State University of Moldova, Republic of Moldova, Victoria Condrea, PhD Student, State University of Moldova, Republic of Moldova, *THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MALADAPTIVE COGNITIVE PATTERNS AND GLYCATED HEMOGLOBIN IN ADOLESCENTS WITH TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS*
12. Daniela Moldoveanu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Military Technical Academy “Ferdinand I”, Bucharest, *NEW AND OLD BENCHMARKS IN THE STUDY OF COMMUNICATION: TRUTH, REALITY, FAKE NEWS*
13. Ştefan Dumitru, Lecturer, PhD, “Carol I” National Defence University, Bucharest, *THREE TYPES OF VULNERABILITIES IN THE NEGOTIATION PROCESS*

14. Călin-Daniel Pațulea, Lecturer, PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *APOSTOLIC AND PAULINE PATERNITY THROUGH SUFFERING AND THE GOSPEL*
15. Brîndușa Maria Popa, Lecturer, PhD, “Carol I” National Defence University, Bucharest, *MASTERING PERCEPTION: THE ART AND SCIENCE OF COMMUNICATION FRAMING*
16. Octav-Sorin Candel, Lecturer, PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *BETRAYAL TRAUMA AND ITS EFFECTS ON ROMANTIC RELATIONSHIPS – A SHORT NARRATIVE REVIEW*
17. Ingrid Cezarina-Elena Ciochină, Lecturer, PhD, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *PRESCHOOL AND LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT*
18. Viorel Nistor, Lecturer, PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *JOURNALISM IN ELECTIONS*
19. Valentin-Sorin Popescu, Lecturer, PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” Christian University, Bucharest, *THE DYNAMICS OF PRE-UNIVERSITY EDUCATION GOVERNANCE IN THE CONTEXT OF THE APPLICATION OF THE NEW LAW ON PRE-UNIVERSITY EDUCATION*
20. Maria-Nicoleta Ciocian, Assist. Prof., PhD „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE UNIVERSITY EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE POST-COVID-19 PANDEMIC PERIOD. UNCERTAINTIES, CHALLENGES, DIRECTIONS AND METHODOLOGICAL PRACTICES. THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM MODEL. THE CASE OF ROMANIA AND EASTERN EUROPE*
21. Violeta Bercaru Oneata, PhD, „I. L. Caragiale” National College, Ploiești, *COMPOSITE MONADS*
22. Alexandra-Georgiana Poenaru, PhD, „Roman-Vodă” National College, *THE EXPLOITATION OF ROMANIAN MIGRANTS IN ITALY. THE CAPORALATO PHENOMENON*

23. Adela Sava (Codreș), PhD, University of Craiova, *SUITE FRANÇAISE, A REALISTIC NOVEL*
24. Victoria Condrea, PhD Student, State University of Moldova, Republic of Moldova, *DIFFERENCES IN THE MANIFESTATION OF BODY DISSATISFACTION IN ADOLESCENTS WITH AND WITHOUT TYPE 1 DIABETES*
25. Dan-Laurențiu Cardaș-Răduța, PhD Student, West University of Timișoara, *MEDIA EDUCATION IN ROMANIA: THE PERCEPTION OF MIDDLE SCHOOL STUDENTS ABOUT THIS CONCEPT*
26. Dan-Laurențiu Cardaș-Răduța, PhD Student, West University of Timișoara, *NEO-NATIONALISM, PROPAGANDA AND RATIONALITY IN RUSSIAN EDUCATION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE WAR WITH UKRAINE*
27. Maria-Gabriela Ilisie, PhD Student, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *MANAGEMENT OF OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AMONG TEACHERS – A KEY COMPONENT OF CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT*
28. Péter István, PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *EXPLORING STUDENT LABOR MARKETS ACROSS EUROPE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS*
29. Onița Pavelea, PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL SKILLS IN PRESCHOOLERS IN THE AGE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE*
30. Smărăndița-Elena Costin, MA Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *COMMUNICATION AS STORYTELLING IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS: DIDACTIC PERSPECTIVES*
31. Maria Gurcova, PhD Student, State University of Moldova, *THE EFFECTS AND IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION THROUGH MUSIC SESSIONS (MUSIC THERAPY SESSIONS) ON THE*

PSYCHOLOGICAL ESTATE AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN STUDENTS WITH AUTISM

32. Gorzo Palaga, PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, *PERSON AND FREEDOM, A PERSPECTIVE ON EDUCATION ACCORDING TO ROMANO GUARDINI*
33. Rodica Pentea Pop, PhD Student, University of Oradea, *RELEVANT ISSUES CONCERNING THE WELL-BEING OF ROMA CHILDREN IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM*

SATURDAY – 18 MAY 2024

***HISTORY, POLITICAL SCIENCES, INTERNATIONAL
RELATIONS***

Moderators: Prof. Mădălina Strehie, PhD, University of Craiova; Assoc. Prof. Rodica Brad, PhD, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu; Assoc. Prof. Ecaterina Hlihor, PhD, “Carol I” National Defence University, Bucharest

1. Mădălina Strehie, Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *CAESAR AND HIS WAR FOR A NEW ROME*
2. Ecaterina Hlihor, Assoc. Prof., PhD, “Carol I” National Defence University, Bucharest, *PUBLIC DIPLOMACY IN TIME OF WAR. ISRAEL'S WAR ON GAZA CASE STUDY*
3. Rodica Brad, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *HISTORICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS FROM THE LIFE OF PEOPLE LIVING IN GURA RÂULUI, PAST AND PRESENT, REFLECTED IN MONOGRAPHS AND LOCAL SOURCES*
4. Andreea Iliescu, Senior Lecturer, PhD, University of Craiova, *CULTURAL SENSITIVITY, WOVEN INTO THE FABRIC OF BUSINESS SAVVY*
5. Arthur Mihăilă, Lecturer, PhD, „Babeş-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *ETHICAL, LEGAL AND POLITICAL IMPLICATIONS OF PREVENTIVE WAR*
6. Laura Ardelean, Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, *CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE ORIGINS AND THE FAMILY OF JOHN VITEZ OF SREDNA*

7. Mihaela Postolache, Lecturer, PhD, „Spiru Haret” University, *IMPLICATIONS OF GLOBALISATION FOR STATE POWER AND SECURITY SINCE THE 20TH CENTURY*
8. Oana-Mihaela Vladu, Lecturer, PhD, ”Carol I” National Defence University, Bucharest, *A POLEMOLOGY PERSPECTIVE ON DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON SECURITY*
9. Ștefan Lifa, Lecturer, PhD, West University of Timișoara, Alexandru Fodor, MA Student, West University of Timișoara, *CONSIDERATIONS ON THE VOIVODESHIPS OF GELU, GLAD AND MENUMORUT IN THE LIGHT OF LITERARY SOURCES*
10. Fábíán István, Lecturer, PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *HISTORY AND PUBLIC OR THE CHALLENGES OF HISTORICAL REENACTMENT IN ROMANIA*
11. Simion Costea, Senior Lecturer, PhD, Global Governance Institute, UMFST Târgu Mureș, Maria Costea, PhD, Scientific Researcher, Romanian Academy’s Institute for Social Sciences and Humanities „Gheorghe Șincai” Târgu Mureș, *FOSTERING GLOBAL ECONOMIC COLLABORATION AND DÉTENTE: PIERRE HARMEL’S MOSCOW VISIT, JULY 24-25, 1969*
12. Valentin Trifescu, PhD, Brukenthal National Museum, Sibiu, *HUNGARIAN PAINTERS FROM THE CONTEMPORARY ART COLLECTION OF THE BRUKENTHAL NATIONAL MUSEUM*
13. Laura Ardelean, Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, Cristian Apati, PhD, archivist, Bihor County National Archives Service, *UNPUBLISHED DOCUMENTS FROM BIHOR REGARDING THE LAST MAJOR CHOLERA EPIDEMIC (1873)*
14. Ferencz Iozsef Truța, Research Assistant, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities of the Romanian Academy, Târgu Mureș, *THE NATIONALIST*

DISCOURSE OF THE '80S. INTERWAR LANDMARKS. FROM GREEN TO RED

15. Narcis-Mihai Martiniuc, Research Assistant, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences, Târgu Mureș, *THE DIVER OF NATURE AND SPIRITUAL WORLDS: ASPECTS FROM ROMANIAN INTERWAR ANTHROPOLOGY*
16. Vasile Pleșca, Scientific Researcher III, PhD, „Gh. Zane” Institute of Economic and Social Research, Romanian Academy, Iași, *HOW DEMOCRACY CAN WORK*
17. Florin F. Nacu, Scientific Researcher III, PhD, ICSU „C.S. Nicolăescu-Plopșor”, Romanian Academy, Craiova, *ROMANIAN SOCIETY AND CULTURE BETWEEN DIFFERENCES, TRADITIONAL WAY OF THINKING AND PATTERN DEPENDENCE (1848-1948)*
18. Tatiana Scurtu, Scientific Researcher, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences, Târgu Mureș, *LEGISLATIVE REGULATIONS REGARDING MILITARY SERVICE, ENSURING PUBLIC HEALTH, PAYING TAXES AND OTHER ASPECTS OF ROMANIAN COMMUNITY LIFE IN THE THREE SEATS COUNTY (1700-1850)*
19. Cristian Apati, PhD, archivist, Bihor County National Archives Service, *ORTHODOX CHURCHES, PRIESTS AND BELIEVERS IN BIHOR IN 1860*
20. Bogdan Iulian Ranteș, PhD, *FOR THE FIRST TIME ON AFRICAN SOIL. NICOLAE CEAUȘESCU'S VISIT TO MOROCCO (DECEMBER 7-11, 1970)*
21. Ștefan Colbu, PhD, „Mihai Eminescu” Central University Library of Iași, *MIGRATION IN TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY – ETHICAL IMPLICATIONS OF POLICIES*
22. Mihaela Gheorghe, PhD, Argeș County Library ”Dinicu Golescu”, *THE REPRESSIVE DIMENSION OF COMMUNISM*

23. Ștefan Dregheci, PhD, Technological High School, Sighișoara, *ASTRA AND THE DOUBLE MONARCHY AT THE END OF THE XIX CENTURY*
24. Ioana Hapca, PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, Teodor-Ioan Hodor, PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *ROMANIA'S COHESION POLICY IN THE ERA OF GDPR: A CASE STUDY OF THE EDUCATION AND EMPLOYMENT PROGRAM*
25. Daniel Ene, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *ROMAN RELIGIOUS TERMS*
26. Maria-Mădălina Bulancia, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *MAJOR THEMES AND SOURCES OF RHETORIC IN THE CURRENT CHINESE POLITICAL DISCOURSE*
27. Mircea-Damian Câmpean, PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *ROMANIAN EDUCATION IN GHERLA THROUGH THE AUSTRO-HUNGARIAN DUALISM AND COMMUNIST REGIME*
28. Victor Risciuc, PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *AMERICAN ECHOES AND IMAGES IN ROMANIAN CULTURE AND PROJECTIONS OF THE ROMANIAN SPACE IN THE AMERICAN WORLD. FROM THE BEGINNING TO THE END OF THE 19TH CENTURY*
29. Andrei Mic, PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE JOURNEY TO CONSTANTINOPOL, OR A LESSER-KNOWN ASPECT OF THE BIOGRAPHY OF A TRANSYLVANIAN INTELLECTUAL: EMIL TIȘÇA (1881-1965)*
30. Ana-Monica Crăciuneanu, PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *SPECULUM LAPIDUM, BETWEEN CAMILLO LEONARDI AND LODOVICO DOLCE. A MATTER OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY AND PRIVILEGE*

31. Ana-Monica Crăciuneanu, PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *THE ROLE OF AMBER IN SIXTEENTH-CENTURY FLORENCE*
32. Anca Mariana Lazea, PhD Student, West University of Timișoara, *WE'RE HISTORY, SO LET'S TELL A NICE STORY. IDENTITY IN DIALOGUE WITH INTERCULTURALITY*

SATURDAY – 18 MAY 2024

SOCIAL SCIENCES

Moderators: Prof. Lucreția Dogaru, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Prof. Ioana-Iulia Olaru, PhD, „George Enescu” National University of Arts, Iași; Prof. Anca-Ileana Dușcă, PhD, University of Craiova

1. Elena Doval, Prof., PhD, „Spiru Haret” University of Bucharest, *THE IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON BUSINESS COMMUNICATION IN EUROPEAN COMPANIES*
2. Lucreția Dogaru, Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *PRECLASSICAL ORIENTATIONS IN CRIMINOLOGY AND THE EARLY REQUIREMENTS OF CRIMINAL LAW*
3. Lucreția Dogaru, Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *SOME ASPECTS RELATED THE LIMITATION OF THE BINDING FORCE OF CONTRACTS: UNPREDICTABILITY OF CONTRACT*
4. Ioana-Iulia Olaru, Prof., PhD, „George Enescu” National University of Arts, Iași, *STYLISTIC FEATURES OF PALEOLITHIC PAINTING*
5. Anca Ileana Dușcă, Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *TRANSPORT OF ELECTRICITY AND PROBLEMS ARISING FROM CUSTOMS DUTIES AND CHARGES WITH EQUIVALENT EFFECT*
6. Bleiziffer William, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE PLACE AND IMPORTANCE OF THE LAITY IN THE CHURCH: A CANONICAL PERSPECTIVE ON THEIR TEACHING FUNCTION*

7. Corina Nani, Assoc. Prof., PhD, West University of Timișoara, *STREET ART BETWEEN DISCOURSE AND ACTION IN PUBLIC SPACE*
8. Ingrid Ileana Nicolau, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Spiru Haret” University of Constanța, *ASPECTS OF WORK PLACE BULLYING/MORAL HARASSMENT*
9. Oana Elena Iacob, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *ASPECTS REGARDING CONSOLIDATED COOPERATION AND THE IMPORTANCE OF ITS IMPLEMENTATION*
10. Lilia Șargu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova, National Institute of Economic Research, *THE CURRENTNESS AND DIVERSIFICATION OF THE PHENOMENON OF RESILIENCE IN CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY*
11. Maria Oroian, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureș, Talita Pascu, Lecturer, PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureș, Raluca-Emilia Moldovan, Lecturer, PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureș, *THE ROLE OF WOMEN AS “LIVING HUMAN TREASURES” IN RURAL DEVELOPMENT. CASE STUDIES IN SIBIU COUNTY, ROMANIA*
12. Lia-Maria Cioanca, Lecturer, PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *FAVORABLE ELEMENTS FOR RURAL TOURISM IN MĂGURI-RĂCĂȚĂU COMMUNE, CLUJ COUNTY, ROMANIA*
13. Doina Guriță, Lecturer, PhD, „Petre Andrei” University of Iași, *GIFT GIVING AND HOLIDAYS OF THE ROMANIAN CONSUMER*
14. Florin Coman, Lecturer, PhD, „Artifex” University of Bucharest, *TAX AND ACCOUNTING IMPLICATIONS AT THE LEVEL OF COMMERCIAL COMPANIES IN ROMANIA REGARDING RO E-INVOICE B2B*

15. Marina Loredana Belu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Craiova, *THE EMPLOYEE'S OBLIGATION TO RESPECT DISCIPLINE IN THE WORKPLACE*
16. Oriana Helena Negulescu, Lecturer, PhD, „Transilvania” University of Braşov, *THE CONFLICTS INSIDE THE ORGANIZATION AND USING THEM AS A POSITIVE FORCE TOWARD PERFORMANCE*
17. Raluca Ionuşa Leotescu, Lecturer, PhD, „Petroleum-Gas” University of Ploieşti, *RESEARCH ON PEDOGENETIC PROCESSES IN THE PICIOR DE MUNTE PLAIN*
18. Niadi-Corina Cernica, Lecturer, PhD, „Ştefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *TIME AS IMMEDIATE EVIDENCE IN WORK OF KANT AND BERGSON*
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20. Camelia Nicoleta Medeleanu, Lecturer, PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iaşi, Mihaela Dana Ignat, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iaşi, *THE INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL STRESS ON PROFESSIONAL PERFORMANCE*
21. Ionela Cecilia Şulea, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureş, Zamfira Maria Căbuz, Teacher in state gymnasium education and Educational adviser, Mureş County School Inspectorate, *CIVIL LIABILITY IN THE FIELD OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY. ETHICAL AND COMMUNICATION ISSUES*

22. Monica Alina Toma, Assist. Prof., PhD, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, *BORDERS AND MEMORY IN LEN WISEMAN'S TOTAL RECALL (2012)*
23. Loredana-Maria Ilin-Grozoiu, 3rd Degree Scientific Researcher PhD, "C. S. Nicolăescu-Plopșor" Institute for Research in Social Studies and Humanities from Craiova, of the Romanian Academy, *THE APPLE / THE APPLE BRANCH - SYMBOLISM IN THE TRADITIONS OF THE CALENDAR AND LIFE CYCLES*
24. Ionel Leonida, Scientific Researcher III, "Victor Slăvescu" Centre for Financial and Monetary Research, Bucharest, Romania, *AN EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS ON THE PROCESS OF FISCAL INTEGRATION AND THE PROSPECT OF A FISCAL UNION IN THE EUROPEAN UNION*
25. Alina Georgeta Ailincă, PhD., 3rd degree researcher, Centre for Financial and Monetary Research "Victor Slăvescu", Bucharest, *CONSIDERATIONS ON WORLDWIDE TAX REVENUES IN THE PERSPECTIVE OF STRENGTHENING FISCAL CAPACITY*
26. Georgiana Chițiga, Scientific Researcher, „Victor Slăvescu” Centre for Financial and Monetary Research, *THE POWER OF POLITICAL ACTION IN CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION*
27. Nicoleta Mihăilă, Scientific Researcher III, PhD, „Victor Slăvescu” Centre for Financial and Monetary Research, *ANALYSIS OF THE STANDARD OF LIVING IN ROMANIA AND SEVERAL MEMBER STATES OF THE EUROPEAN UNION. CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES*
28. Gabriela-Cornelia Piciu, Senior Researcher, PhD, "Victor Slăvescu" Centre for Financial and Monetary Research, Romanian Academy, Bucharest, *CONTROVERSIES AND PERSPECTIVES OF CLIMATE POLICY IN CHINA*

29. Georgeta Ghionea, Researcher III, PhD, "C. S. Nicolăescu Ploșor" Institute for Research in Social Studies and Humanities from Craiova, of the Romanian Academy, *ECONOMIC AND CULTURAL ADVERTISING IN ROMANIAN PERIODICAL*
30. Anca Ceaușescu, 3rd degree Scientific Researcher PhD, "C. S. Nicolăescu Ploșor", Institute for Researches Social Studies and Humanities from Craiova, of the Romanian Academy, *BRIEF INQUIRY INTO THE WORK OF C. S. NICOLĂESCU-PLOȘOR. CONTRIBUTION TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF ROMANIAN ETHNOGRAPHY AND GEOGRAPHY*
31. Alexandru-Ioan Cînda, PhD, West University of Timișoara, *THE IDEA OF LOCUS AS A PREREQUISITE IN LATIN MYSTICISM. A PHILOSOPHICAL VIEW ON NUMINOUS SPATIALITY*
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34. Corina Tonita, PhD, C. J. R. A. E. Dolj, *THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE APPROACH TO DYSLEXIA-DYSGRAPHIA*
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36. Nicoleta-Raina Geamalinga, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *LAW, HAPPINESS AND GLOBALIZATION AT THE WORKPLACE*

37. Tatiana Păncescu (Valea), PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *TYPES OF MOTIVATION USED IN MANAGERIAL PRACTICE*
38. Tatiana Păncescu (Valea), PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *THE MOTIVATION - PERFORMANCE RELATIONSHIP*
39. Dan Mihalcea, PhD Student, „Babeş-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *EXPRESS YOURSELF, DON'T REPRESS YOURSELF!*
40. Iuliana Anane, PhD Student, National School of Political and Administrative Studies, *SOCIAL AND LEGAL IMPLICATIONS OF DIGITALIZATION IN THE ROMANIAN PUBLIC SECTOR*
41. Anca Bonto, PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, *ELEMENTS OF WESTERN ESOTERICISM AS A FORM OF THOUGHT*
42. Daniel Băncilă, PhD Student, University of European Studies, Moldova, *SIMULATION. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ASPECTS*
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45. Ani Emilia Cernea-Radu, PhD Student, University of Oradea, *SOCIAL INDICATORS OF THE CHILDREN'S QUALITY OF LIFE*
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47. Crina-Maria Stanciu, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *“TO PROMISE” - APPLICATIONS OF GOOD FAITH IN SUCCESSION MATTERS THROUGH TRUST*
48. Alexandru Bogdan Romaniuc, PhD Student, „Babeş-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *NEW FORMS OF CRIME AT THE BORDER WITH UKRAINE, MARAMUREŞ AREA*
49. Anca-Steliana Mirea, PhD Student, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, *A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS ON LITHIUM EXTRACTION AS A SOLUTION TO CLIMATE CHANGE*
50. Mihai Liviu Marici, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THEOLOGICAL DIMENSIONS OF COMMUNICATION*
51. Tiberiu Nicușor Chiriluşă, PhD Student, Bucharest Academy of Economic Studies, *THE ANOMALOUS SUCCESSION - THE EXCEPTION TO THE RULE OF THE SUCCESSIONAL TRANSMISSION*
52. Alina-Daiana Vaş, PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, North University Centre of Baia Mare, *MODERN TOLERANCE - THE CITIZEN, TOLERANCE AND HUMAN SOLIDARITY*

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